

Financial Literacy in Schools:

The faults of financial literacy education and how they can be addressed

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Abstract

Financial literacy is an essential life skill that allows people to manage personal finances effectively; however, many students graduate without the necessary skills or knowledge to navigate credit, investments, and personal finance effectively. This paper examines the severity of effects of this issue, then analyzes the root causes, and finally proposes potential solutions at the individual and societal levels. Existing research indicates that poor financial literacy is associated with eventual poor financial habits. Studies also show that some current financial education programs are ineffective due to low student motivation and poor curriculum quality. To further examine this issue, a survey of 26 high school students was conducted to determine student confidence in their financial literacy. The results indicated that students feel highly unprepared to measure adult financial responsibilities despite that many have taken an economics course. The findings of this survey also indicated that discussions of family finances at home boost student confidence. This research concludes that improving financial literacy requires additional at home education and improvements in school education around this subject. Internalization of financial education could be greatly improved if taught through multiple sources.

Introduction

Imagine your kids' futures. They did everything right: got good grades, went to college, got a good job. Now imagine this: they take out large loans with high interest rates, they rack up credit card debt, they buy a car they can't afford, and eventually spiral into unrelenting debt. This is not a result of your bad parenting, nor is it the fault of your children, this is a result of a major fault in the public school system. Every day millions of students across the US go to school, hoping to learn life skills that will permit them to function as an adult in society.

It's no secret that schools lack education in practical skills, one of the most important being financial literacy. Anyone can get a job and make money, but this education allows you to grow, take care of, and maintain it. Financial literacy is a highly important aspect of a child's preparation for adulthood, allowing them to make smart financial decisions for the rest of their life. For the purposes of this paper I will define financial literacy as the ability of an individual to make logical decisions regarding management of money, spending, credit, debt, and investments. This particularly regards personal finance, where I will explore effects, causes, and potential solutions to this arising issue.

There are multiple ways to view this issue, whether you consider it a failure of the education system, or an issue for at-home education, one thing is for sure: the effects of inadequate financial education can be detrimental to the integration of a young adult into society. This paper explores various areas related to this topic including: What are the long term effects of this injustice? Where does it come from and are schools really at fault? What can we do both as a society and as individuals to rectify this problem in our education system?

Literature Review

Effects

One of the biggest effects of financial illiteracy is increased poverty levels. A peer reviewed article by Leonore Riitsalu (2016), Exploring Causes, Effects, and Solutions to Financial Illiteracy and Exclusion among Minority Demographic Groups, provides an analysis of the factors that contribute to financial illiteracy and poverty. Figure 2 is a graph comparing financial literacy rates to poverty levels, showing a moderate to strong direct correlation between the two variables. This graph directly shows how poverty and financial illiteracy are highly associated. Additionally, this article shows how financial literacy is associated with better financial decisions such as usage of bigger banks and not being taken advantage of by predatory loans. Table 2 (Riitsalu 2016) shows how people who used traditional banking scored ~50% higher on an economic literacy test. This further shows how financial literacy contributes positively to financial wellbeing. If more people were financially literate, poverty levels would decrease and unfortunate financial predicaments would be far less common. Although higher financial literacy rates would benefit many, those who engage in shady loans would suffer. This would destroy the jobs of people who make money through quick loans and taking advantage of ill-informed people.

Another major effect is foolish spending and financial habits. A peer-reviewed article by Mitchell (2017), published by the National Library of Medicine, shows how financially literate people are more likely to save, invest, and not have high debt. Their findings show that financially literate people “have been shown to be less likely to have credit card debt, and when they do borrow, they manage loans better.” (Mitchell, 2017) They also note that “Financial knowledge can also pay off in terms of saving and investment efficiency” (Mitchell, 2017) They

particularly stress the importance of good financial decision making during times of instability, highlighting how 1 wrong move can be detrimental. These effects are undeniable. It is critical that we work to improve financial literacy programs in schools and better educate the youth about better money habits. A differing perspective could suggest that these poor monetary habits aren't caused by financial illiteracy, but rather the opposite. "Perhaps some people are savvier because they have more money in the first place." (Mitchell, 2017) It's really a question of correlation vs causation. Does poverty come from a lack of financial understanding, or does a lack of financial education lead to poverty? Perhaps it's a little bit of both. Either way, we need to work to solve this problem. Financial illiteracy is a major problem that plagues our society and negatively affects already poor communities.

Causes

We know why financial illiteracy is a problem, but what is the cause? Brentin Mock's (2017) Bloomberg article overviews a major problem in schools. A high school in Harrisburg, Pennsylvania "suspended half of its student population for excessive absences." Kids in school are highly unmotivated leading to a rise in truancy. Not only are kids ditching school, but when they do go, they don't care and don't try to learn. Mock proposes a radical solution: paying the kids a salary to go to school. The article suggests one major cause of truancy in these impoverished communities, is to go to work to support the family. If kids got paid to go to school, they could earn money while still learning. Not only would this solve the issue of motivation, but it would help teach kids to manage money in the process. Although this seems appealing on the surface, the issue of the money to pay them quickly arises. Schools are underfunded as it is, so how could they possibly afford to pay all their students? He article suggests limiting this benefit to only lower-income students. This would limit necessary funds,

and help improve wealth inequality. Although this solution is extremely radical, it illustrates the extremity of issues in education. Kids are forced to go to school against their will, and this leads to highly unmotivated learners.

More specifically pertaining to finance, A peer reviewed article by Martha Henn McCormick (2013), *The Effectiveness of Youth Financial Education: A Review of the Literature*, shows additional causes of financial illiteracy and low motivation in schools. Perhaps many don't think it's important, or lack the motivation to learn about finance. "Low financial literacy scores among young adults, even after they have taken a course in personal finance, is related to lack of motivation to learn or retain these skills" (McCormick, 2013). These are necessary life skills that help you make smarter financial decisions. This is why it's critical to highlight the benefits to better motivate students and participants of financial literacy courses. With better motivation, the participants could be better engaged and therefore retain the information being taught better. Although higher motivation would improve the effectiveness of these courses, the quality of financial education is highly questionable. "Unfortunately, we do not find conclusive evidence that, in general, financial education programs do lead to greater financial knowledge, and, ultimately, to better financial behavior" (McCormick, 2013). The lack of quality in existing education begs the question: should kids even be motivated in the first place?

Solutions

One societal solution to financial illiteracy is public resources. Outside of school classes and specific courses, public resources can be a great way for individuals to explore financial topics. The Office of Comptroller of the Currency has published a public resource directory containing various resources to learn about financial topics. "This resource directory includes links and brief descriptions of some federal government sources and nonprofit organizations that

provide financial literacy and education, publications, programs, and other resources” (Financial Literacy Resource Directory). Many public resources like this and others are a great way to help people learn about these complex topics. Although this is a great way to learn about finance, the problem of unmotivated students still persists. In the end, we can’t force students to be interested in a topic, we can only provide the resources necessary for them if they desire to learn. This is only 1 public resource, and without people going out of their way to research finance, this won’t solve the problem.

Another more out of the ordinary individual solution is social media. Social media is a great way to learn things and reach a broader audience. Intuit Credit Karma’s (2022) article, Gen Z learns more about money from social media influencers than school or books, study shows, notes a study concluding that “Nearly a quarter of Gen Z respondents say social media influencers have taught them the most about money, more than school or books.” Maybe instead of forcing students to sit in schools, they could better learn these topics through viewing and interacting with engaging videos. Making educational videos in a fun and interactive way can help people to learn. Although social media allows us to reach vast audiences with minimal effort, critics argue that social media financial content can be oversimplified, misleading, or driven by influencers that prioritize engagement over accuracy. Despite this, I still believe that social media educational content holds great potential, and with factually accurate information, it can help educate millions at a time.

Conclusion

In summary, financial illiteracy is a major problem plaguing society. It leads to worse financial decisions down the line and increased poverty levels, and increases the likelihood of bad debt. Causes include school truancy, being unmotivated, bad quality of financial literacy

programs, and simply not caring. We can begin to solve this problem by increasing access to financial literacy resources and creating engaging educational videos to publish on social media, reaching millions in the process. Although we can strive to solve this issue, there remains the complexity of how we can access communities that simply do not care. We can not be certain of whether financial illiteracy causes poverty, or if having wealth is what motivates people to become financially literate.

Primary Research

Methods and Participants

To better research the causes, effects, and possible solutions to this issue, I have conducted a survey consisting of 14 questions and 26 respondents. Questions consisted of things such as personal and financial background to better gain a better understanding of the respondents socioeconomic status, as well as questions to better poll overall financial literacy. I chose to conduct a survey to better gather quantitative data that will allow me to generalize and analyze the state of the people whom this issue affects. I conducted this research using google forms using mostly multiple choice questions that allowed participants to input a range of agreement as well as a couple of checkbox questions and one free response to get an idea of overall sentiment. In order to conduct this survey I was forced to assume respondents would be primarily UHS students meaning they were all required to take an economics class sometime throughout high school. The survey was distributed both on our class canvas page as well as on my personal Instagram over the course of a week. Although these methods aren't perfect, as it only takes data from a single high school and primarily Juniors, this primary research should still give a general idea of the state of financial education among highschoolers.

This survey is by no means perfect, however it should still give a general idea of the state of financial literacy, at least in this school. My survey had 26 respondents consisting of 77% male and 85% junior which highlights the bias for who decided to respond, although the problem of Juniors primarily arises due to the methods of survey distribution. The respondents came from houses of varied family income with a slight bias towards the upper class, however the main bias that may arise due to the demographic is that most contestants attend UHS, a school known for its academic rigor. This is shown through how 73% had an unweighted GPA of above 3.7 and none of the contestants had less than a B average. The average contestant will also have taken ~10 AP classes by the end of this school year. The polling also indicated an even spread between those who take AP Econ vs Honors Econ, as Economics is a required class. This is the demographic that was available, however this works because it allows me to study the core group affected by this topic. The limitations of this are that it does not include a rural population nor data from a less academically adept high school.

Results and Discussion

The results of the survey indicate that financial education programs in schools do not adequately prepare students for the real world of personal finance. The survey concluded that 69% of students feel unprepared to handle taxes, 58% feel unprepared to handle investments, and 54% feel unprepared to handle student loans/paying for college. This indicates how students feel unprepared, and almost failed by the school system, especially since 73% indicated having already taken an Econ class. This not only shows that students feel unprepared, but that the neglect of adequate financial education in schools can have real tangible effects late in life. This conclusion is not necessarily absolute as the limitations of demographic may show that it can be more effective for other students; however, this almost strengthens the argument of poor

financial education since some of the highest level students in the area still feel unprepared to handle adult finances. Mitchell indicates how financial knowledge has high potential to pay off in the long term (2017). This data reinforces that by showing the potential extent of the persistence of this issue. So why is this issue not talked about more? I believe that since this can potentially have such drastic implications, it should be a priority to improve the financial literacy of highschoolers.

Financial literacy is not only caused by a lack of quality in-school education, the causes of this issue extend into the home. Results indicate that 58% of contestants felt that school does not adequately prepare students to manage finances in the world; however, students who indicated that they talked about finances often at home showed significantly higher confidence in managing personal finances than those who indicated they did not discuss it much at home. The students who discussed it often averaged a 4.5/5 in confidence vs those who did not discuss it averaged 2.3/5. This shows that both school and at-home education can be major causes of financial illiteracy. Despite this, widespread betterment of school education has already been a heated topic, and although some efforts persist, such a solution may be unrealistic. One thing parents can do is to just discuss it more at home. It's amazing how much of an effect just a little bit of discussion at home can have. Again, this data is limited to a small sample size but I believe the effects of discussing finance at home are strictly positive, so it can't hurt. This contrast with alternative places to learn is reinforced by McCormick, whose own study showed that in-school financial education is highly ineffective, also turning to other potentially better modes of education (2013). This is highly significant because it suggests that a pivot away from traditional education systems could be beneficial, however, schools are not always a completely ineffective way to learn.

I believe that the 2 best solutions to this persisting issue are to talk about finances more at home, and that high schools should require a personal finance course to graduate. The data suggests that at home and school were the 2 main ways students learned about finances. At home was above all with 89%, and only 50% learned it from school. Additionally, 92% indicated that they would be in favor of a personal finance graduation requirement, and responses to the free response question further indicated this trend, with responses such as “Make it an actual class on budgeting and finances.” These responses show an overwhelming indication that in-school financial literacy needs reform, and that personal finance should be a requirement. Many students don’t believe in the effectiveness of existing systems. Although my respondents were highly enthusiastic about in-school financial education, the indirect data shows that education at home can be far more effective, almost disagreeing with the determined causes . That being said, talking about finance at home can still be an easy way to drastically improve this issue, but the implementation of both of these solutions side by side would help more than either one by itself. An article by Intuit Credit Karma had similar findings, they determined that social media was a major source of financial education, but similarly concluded that school was less important than we may have thought. Over 70% of US high schools already require a personal finance course, but imagine how much better it could be if it was 100%. These findings are significant because it shows that students learn from a variety of sources, and expecting them to learn everything in 1 place is silly. This goes for every topic too, but a combination of learning from family, friends, social media, being self taught, and school classes, makes for a more well-rounded and higher quality education that would be unattainable just from learning in one place.

Conclusion

Overall, this research revealed that in-school financial education can often be ineffective. The research showed that students get their education from a variety of sources, not just school. At home education, even if just discussing family finances, can be a great way to fill gaps in personal knowledge. Lack of quality education in this field can have major life consequences in the future so it's important to work to better the poorer parts of the American education system. This survey helped fill the gaps in existing research of student sentiment and has helped me to conclude that alternative modes of education are necessary. Although this research has brought much new insight, it could be useful to further inquire about the differences between different modes of education, and how these results vary across other high schools and different demographics.

Conclusion

School is a failing system, but we can rectify this issue outside of traditional education. As individuals—particularly parents—we can work to better this issue by discussing finance at home. What happens to those children who did everything else right when they get adequate financial education? Just by talking about this subject at home, we could improve youth's skills in management of finances, allowing them to not make grave mistakes, and leading to a brighter financial future. If parents were to discuss finances with their kids, it could rectify many of the faults of the school system, allowing children to still get the education they need without major education reform. Although this may be a sensitive topic for many families, it can help their children make better choices in the future, so the tradeoff is worth it. The difference really can be night and day.

School, home, and social media are all great places to learn, (parallelism) but a combination of these would provide the best education. School is a failing system, but it can be salvaged. Implementation of new administrative education practices can fix many of the issues that persist in public education. One main way that could easily improve the state of this issue is by requiring a personal finance course in schools. As we continue to face this issue, and individuals fail to be educated on this subject, we can work to implement a personal finance requirement in high schools across the U.S. This solution would lead to an overall increase in financial literacy rates nationwide, which could lead to alleviation of this issue on a large scale, allowing young adults across the nation to make better decisions, and helping them integrate into society. School administration and lawmakers must work together to achieve this goal, and although it may be difficult to make this widespread, we can always start at the local level.

Annotated Bibliography

McCormick, Martha Henn. "The Effectiveness of Youth Financial Education: A Review of the Literature." *Papers.ssrn.com*, 27 Feb. 2013, papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2225339.

This paper explores the current state of youth financial literacy education. It uses data and comprehensive analysis to gain a better understanding of the current state of financial education, and measures its effectiveness. This is a highly credible research bias with very minimal bias making it a highly useful paper to reference to gain a baseline understanding of prior research in this topic. Because this paper explores many of the same issues as my own, It's a great resource to reference and build off of. In this paper, I use this article as a reference to understand the root causes of this issue including lack of motivation, quality, and resources.

Riitsalu, Leonore, and Kaire Põder. "A Glimpse of the Complexity of Factors That Influence Financial Literacy." *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, vol. 40, no. 6, July 2016, pp. 722–31, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12291>.

This paper aims to determine the potential factors that influence a person's financial literacy. It examines test scores in Estonia and looks at the demographic backgrounds' associations with financial literacy scores. It compares the scores to various socioeconomic factors but determines that the biggest indicator of high financial literacy is the amount of books in the household, which can be a strong indicator of a family's status and background. This study is a highly credible paper that has been reviewed by many experts to provide accurate and unbiased information to the reader. This source is useful because it provides some insight into existing research on this topic and helps me to get a strong baseline idea of some of the factors that influence financial literacy. This paper was used to show the correlation between poverty

levels and financial literacy. This study poses some interesting complexity, though, as it begs the question of if low literacy caused poverty, or of poverty led to lower financial literacy.

Mitchell, Olivia S., and Annamaria Lusardi. “Financial Literacy and Economic

Outcomes: Evidence and Policy Implications.” *The Journal of Retirement*, vol. 3, no. 1, June 2015, pp. 107–14, <https://doi.org/10.3905/jor.2015.3.1.107>.

This paper discusses the relationship between financial literacy and financial decision making globally. It finds that financial literacy rates are low in both developed and developing nations. It also finds that this issue is particularly prevalent among women and less educated people. Additionally, this paper analyzes financial literacy particularly among high school students and discusses the high importance of their findings as it pertains to integration of young adults into the financial world. This is a highly credible and unbiased peer reviewed paper and was highly useful to better understand the implications of this prevailing issue. This article was used in this paper to illustrate the importance and effects of this issue, showing that higher financial literacy can lower the likelihood of poverty, increase investment outcomes, and lead to lower debt.

“Financial Literacy Resource Directory.” *Www.occ.gov*, 1 Apr. 2019,

www.occ.gov/topics/consumers-and-communities/community-affairs/resource-directories/financial-literacy/index-financial-literacy-resource-directory.html.

This source is a compilation of resources that could be used for financial literacy education. This list was put together by the Office of the Comptroller of the Currency (OCC), which is a government organization. Although being a .gov website does give it some credibility, this is not a highly vetted source. Although it may be prone to some bias, this source was not used as a resource to draw facts from, but rather as an example of a partial solution implemented

by the government to help mitigate some effects of this issue. Although its use cases in this paper are limited, it serves as an example that resources like this do exist. This solution is not perfect though, because as prior parts of this paper indicated, a major cause of the issue of financial literacy is not a lack of resources, but rather a lack of individuals' motivation to learn.

“Gen Z Learns More about Money from Social Media Influencers than School or Books, Study Shows.” *Intuit Credit Karma*, 5 Apr. 2022,

www.creditkarma.com/about/commentary/gen-z-learns-more-about-money-from-social-media-influencers-than-school-or-books-study-shows.

This Intuit Credit Karma article presents the findings of a recent study of where younger people draw their education. It presents that Gen Z is learning more about finances through online influencers and at home than anywhere else. Because this is a potentially biased institution, we can use the information from this article with caution. Although the institution may be potentially biased, we know that the data within the study is real, allowing us to use the information we need. This paper uses this article to show the influence of media in education, which can present information in far more engaging ways, though with limited detail and accuracy. This article thus strengthens this paper's argument by demonstrating the prevalence of alternative sources of education

Mock, Brentin. “Bloomberg - Are You a Robot?” *Www.bloomberg.com*, 3 Apr. 2017,

www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2017-04-03/pay-teens-to-attend-school-or-keep-losing-them.

This article proposes one possible solution to the lack of motivation in school among students. It proposes the idea of paying students to go to school, which on the surface is unrealistic, but the article states that this cost would be far less than recapturing these youth from

delinquency. It proposes that this solution would lead to increased attendance, decreased truancy, and importantly, an incentive to perform well. This article, originally found in our class's English textbook, is not necessarily a reliable source due to its limited perspective and publishing by a potentially unreliable organization. Despite this, it can be useful in my paper to help illustrate the problem of truancy in schools, and how a major cause of the issue of financial illiteracy is kids not caring about school. This paper uses the article to demonstrate the positive effects of motivation in students, showing that when students care, school education can be somewhat effective.